

THE PRODUCTION OF SHORT ALUMINA-FIBRE/SiC PARTICULATE MMC BY THE MELT INFILTRATION PROCESS

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents details of a novel process route which is capable of producing short-fibre/particulate hybrid Metal Matrix Composites (MMC) by preform infiltration. It is shown that the strengths and elastic moduli of these hybrids are controlled primarily by the total reinforcement volume fraction and not by the particulate/fibre ratio. However this ratio does have a strong influence on the fracture toughness of these hybrid composites.

INTRODUCTION

Currently there is considerable interest in MMC since alloys reinforced with high strength materials represent a unique method for improving mechanical properties such as elastic modulus and strength. Although the improvements associated with particulate reinforced MMC are lower than those observed with other reinforcements these materials are of great technological significance since they exhibit pseudoisotropic properties and are potentially very cheap. Currently these composites are fabricated by powder metallurgy, stir-casting and by spray-forming. However, an additional process should also be attractive on the basis of cost and low particulate/matrix reactivity. This is the preform infiltration route. The principal draw-back of this process is the need for preforms containing substantial amounts of particulate and this has led to only limited exploitation of this technique in the fabrication of particulate reinforced MMC.

The liquid metal infiltration technique requires the production of preforms containing stable dispersions of the reinforcing phase which can then be subsequently infiltrated. The problem with particulate reinforcements is that they cannot be easily preformed into a stable array. Most preforms are produced from short-fibres which pack together and can be 'bound' to produce a rigid array of well-dispersed fibres. The volume fractions of these preforms can also be varied over a wide-range (typically 0.04 - 0.40). However particulates have a low aspect ratio and close-pack during any attempt at preforming. This means that it is not possible to produce preforms with low particulate contents, and the particulate volume fractions cannot be easily varied. However, if particulate/fibre hybrid preforms could be produced the array of fibres could be used to disperse the particulates within the preforms. Such preforms would require a minimum volume-fraction of supportive fibres but could be manufactured with varying volume fractions of particulates. Although these preforms would not produce pure particulate reinforced MMC, this route would offer increased flexibility since a range of preforms could be produced from conventional fibre/particulate hybrids (where the fibre fraction is substantially higher than that of the particulate) to preforms where the fibre fraction is at a minimum and the response of the resulting composites would be dominated by the properties of the particulate (essentially a particulate/fibre hybrid). By selection of a suitable binder it should also be possible to infiltrate these hybrid preforms in an identical manner to that employed for conventional short-fibre preforms. This paper describes a novel process

route which is capable of fabricating such preforms and presents mechanical property data for a series of particulate/fibre hybrid composites produced from these preforms by the pressure infiltration process.

PREFORM MANUFACTURE

Hybrid preforms were manufactured from short alumina fibres and SiC particulates. The fibre employed was SAFFIL (ICI trademark) a 3 μ m diameter short δ -alumina fibre, and the particulates were standard 600 (8 μ m diameter) and 320 (18 μ m) grit SiC abrasives. Preforms were produced by first dispersing the fibre and particulate in an aqueous medium containing a mixed binder of silica and latex, and then settling this dispersion by vacuum-assisted filtration. The particulate/fibre ratios in the final preforms were controlled by altering the relative amounts of the species dispersed in the liquid, and the total reinforcement fraction was controlled by the application of a load during settling. Three types of hybrid preform were manufactured with total volume fractions of 0.30 and varying ratios of particulate and fibre. These ratios varied from 1:1 ($V_p = 0.15:V_f = 0.15$) to 5:1 ($V_p = 0.25:V_f = 0.05$). Preforms consisting of only δ -alumina fibres were also manufactured for comparison with the hybrid materials. After filtration the preforms were slowly dried at 120°C and then fired at 1200°C to generate the mechanical strength required for infiltration.

COMPOSITE FABRICATION AND EVALUATION

Composites were fabricated from these preforms by the liquid infiltration route using aluminium alloy 7039 (Al-4.0Zn-2.0Mg). The experimental details of this process have been described in two earlier papers^{1,2}. The quasi-static mechanical properties of the composites were then determined by tensile testing and the dynamic fracture responses by instrumented charpy testing. The composites were also microstructurally characterised by quantitative optical microscopy and their fracture behaviour was investigated by scanning electron fractography.

RESULTS

Fig 1 shows the microstructures of the conventional short-fibre composite and the various hybrids. These composites were all well-infiltrated and the short-fibre material (fig 1(a)) exhibited a 2-D pseudorandom distribution of fibres which was typical of the microstructures obtained from commercially available fibre preforms^{1,2}. The hybrid composites (fig 1(b,c,d)) contained 2-D random arrangements of the short-fibre which supported well-dispersed SiC particulates, and there was no sign of reaction between the particulates and the matrix alloy. Identical hybrid microstructures were obtained with both the fine and coarse particulates. The particulates were well dispersed in all the hybrids, however, the fibre-fraction did affect the homogeneity of the composites. In low fibre-fraction materials the fibre array was not uniform and the particulates collected in the higher fibre fraction regions. This resulted in decreased homogeneity at higher particulate/fibre ratios. The minimum fibre fraction which could support the particulates was ~ 0.05 . This therefore limited the maximum particulate/fibre ratio in these hybrids to 5:1 ($V_p = 0.25:V_f = 0.05$).

Fig 2 summarises the mechanical properties of these composites. The UTS of the hybrids were marginally lower than those of the δ -alumina fibre composites and exhibited little variation with particulate/fibre ratio. Similar effects were also observed for the yield and 0.2% proof stresses. The yield and proof stress of the hybrids did not depend on the particulate size, however the UTS was marginally lower with coarser particulates. Measurement of the elastic moduli was difficult, however values of Youngs Modulus generally lay between 110 and 120 GPa which was similar to the value obtained on a 0.3 V_f alumina-fibre reinforced composite. Fig 2 also shows that the hardness of these hybrids were independent of particulate/fibre ratio.

The final data in fig 2 shows the effect of particulate/fibre ratio on the dynamic fracture energies. It is clear that as this ratio increased the fracture energy also increased, indicating an

improvement in toughness. The impact (force/time) curves for the hybrids were very similar to those of conventional short-fibre composites. The nature of these curves have been discussed previously³ and the present data shows that the hybrids exhibited a brittle response with a low energy for the propagation of fracture. The curves for all the composites showed an elastic response of similar compliance but a peak-load which increased with particulate/fibre ratio (the variation of this peak-load is shown in fig 3). The size of the particulate had a significant effect on the toughness (fig 2) with coarser particulates resulting in lower toughness levels.

Fig 4 shows fractographs from the impact specimens. There was a continuous transition in the fracture surfaces with increasing particulate/fibre ratio. At low ratios the fracture was dominated by the short-fibres and there was little evidence of matrix ductility. This contrasted with higher ratios where the fracture surface became less dominated by fibre failure and instead by the presence of the particulates. Increasing the fraction of the particulates resulted in more extensive matrix regions which exhibited clear signs of plastic deformation.

DISCUSSION

The results presented above show that it is possible to produce particulate/fibre hybrid MMC by the preform infiltration route, and at the highest particulate/fibre ratios the composite materials are almost identical to conventional particulate reinforced MMC. The distribution of the particulates in these hybrids is inferior to that obtained in extruded PM, stir-cast or spray-formed particulate composites, however, it is superior to all these materials in the as-formed condition. This means that these hybrids have no requirement for further processing and can be fully integrated into any near net-shape liquid infiltration process. The rapid process time also means that there is no particulate/matrix reaction and no additional measures are therefore required to improve wetting or inhibit reactivity⁴.

Little work has been conducted on the mechanical properties of hybrid MMC. The most systematic is that of Towata and Yamada⁵ who have shown that the presence of a particulate improves the strength of SiC continuous fibre reinforced composites. The present work appears to contradict this data. However the present hybrids differ substantially from those of Towata and Yamada. They investigated continuous fibre/particulate hybrids with particulate/fibre ratios of 0.065:1 whereas the present work concentrated on particulate/short-fibre hybrids with ratios between 1:1 and 5:1. These systems lie at opposite extremes of the range of possible hybrids and also differ in the nature of the fibre reinforcement. It is therefore quite conceivable that both sets of data are correct and that in particulate/short-fibre hybrids strength is independent of the particulate/fibre ratio whereas in continuous fibre/particulate hybrids strength improvements can be obtained with the presence of a small volume-fraction of particulates.

However particulate/fibre ratio does play a strong role in controlling the toughness of these hybrid MMC. The force/time curves for these hybrids show that to a first approximation they can be treated by simple elastic fracture mechanics. Such an analysis implies that their dynamic fracture energies (fig 2) are a measure of the critical strain energy release-rate⁶. Since this energy is controlled primarily by the load required to initiate fracture (fig 3) and since the moduli of the hybrids are similar, this suggests that the toughening of these materials with increasing particulate/fibre ratio is associated with an increase in their fracture toughness. Further evidence for this comes from the effect of particulate size on the fracture energy. Fig 2 suggests that the fracture toughness of these hybrids decreases with increasing particulate size. This is consistent with previous observations of the effect of particulate size on the fracture toughness of particulate reinforced MMC⁷.

The improved toughness of these hybrid MMC is interesting since the K_{IC} of particulate reinforced MMC are often reported to be higher than those of short-fibre reinforced composites^{6,8}. This suggests that by altering the ratio of particulate to fibre the toughness of these hybrid MMC can be continuously changed from the low value associated with short-fibre composites (at low particulate/fibre ratios) to the higher values characteristic of particulate

reinforced materials (at high particulate/fibre ratios).

CONCLUSIONS

1. Particulate/fibre hybrid MMC can be produced by the preform infiltration route.
2. At high particulate/fibre ratios these hybrid MMC are almost identical to conventional particulate reinforced materials.
3. The strength, hardness and elastic moduli of these hybrid composites are controlled by the total reinforcement fraction and not by the particulate/fibre ratio.
4. The fracture toughness and dynamic fracture energies of these hybrids depend on the particulate/fibre ratio. These increase at higher ratios due to a change in the fracture process from a fibre to a particulate dominated response.

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Fig.1 Microstructures of conventional short-fibre and particulate/fibre hybrid composites. (a) Conventional composite $V_f=0.30$, (b) $V_p=0.15 : V_f=0.15$ (c) $V_p=0.20 : V_f=0.10$ (d) $V_p=0.25 : V_f=0.05$ (particulate size = $8\mu\text{m}$)

Fig.2 The effect of particulate/fibre ratio on the UTS, hardness and toughness of SiC particulate/short δ -alumina fibre hybrid MMC (\boxplus \oplus data for 320 grit hybrids).

Fig.3 The effect of particulate/fibre ratio on the peak-load developed during instrumented impact testing

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

Fig.4 Fractographs of conventional short-fibre and particulate/fibre hybrid composites (a) conventional composite $V_f=0.30$, (b) $V_p=0.15 : V_f=0.15$, (c) $V_p=0.20 : V_f=0.10$ (d) $V_p=0.25 : V_f=0.05$ (particulate size = $8\mu\text{m}$).